

A Real-Time Blended Energy Management Strategy of Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles Considering Driving Conditions

Abstract: In this study, a blended energy management strategy considering influences of driving conditions is proposed to improve the fuel economy of plug-in hybrid electric vehicles. To attain it, dynamic programming is firstly applied to solve and quantify influences of different driving conditions and driving distances. Then, the driving condition is identified by the K-means clustering algorithm in real time with the help of Global Positioning System and Geographical Information System. A blended energy management strategy is proposed to achieve the real-time energy allocation of the powertrain with incorporation of the identified driving conditions and the extracted rules, which includes the engine starting scheme, gear shifting schedule and torque distribution strategy. Simulation results reveal that the proposed strategy can effectively adapt to different driving conditions with the dramatic improvement of fuel economy and the decrement of calculation intensity and highlight the feasibility of real-time implementation.

Key Words: Plug-in hybrid electric vehicles, energy management strategy, global optimization, driving condition, equivalent driving distance coefficient.

NOMENCLATURE

Abbreviation

PHEV	Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle
HEV	Hybrid Electric Vehicle
AER	All-Electric Range
EMS	Energy Management Strategies
ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
CD-CS	Charge Depletion-Charge Sustaining
SOC	State of Charge
DP	Dynamic Programming
PMP	Pontryagin's Minimum Principle
QP	Quadratic Programming
ECMS	Equivalent Consumption Minimization Strategy
NN	Neural Networks
FL	Fuzzy Logic
GA	Genetic Algorithm
SA	Simulated Annealing

PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization
GPS	Global Positioning System
ITS	Intelligent Transportation System
GIS	Geographical Information System
MPC	Model Prediction Control
SVM	Support Vector Machine
ISG	Integrated Starter Generator
DCT	Dual-Clutch Transmission
OCV	Open Circuit Voltage
DOD	Depth of Discharge

Symbols

M	vehicle mass
f	rolling resistance coefficient
α	road grade
C_D	air drag coefficient
A	frontal area of the vehicle
u	vehicle speed
δ	correction coefficient of rotating mass
η_t	transmission system efficiency
T_e	engine torque
i_{DCT}	transmission ratio
T_v	vehicle demand torque
T_{req}	demand torque of the energy source
T_{all}	duration of the driving cycle
J	total cost for optimization
L	instantaneous cost at each step
N	total steps
x_k	system state
u_k	controlling policies
L_c	instantaneous operating cost
L_g	instantaneous cost for gear shifting
P_f	price of gasoline per liter
$Q_{fuel}(k)$	instantaneous fuel consumption
P_e	price of electricity per kwh

$Q_{ele}(k)$	instantaneous electricity consumption
γ	penalty factor for frequent gear shifting
$J_k^*(x_k)$	the minimum operating cost when the system starts from the k th section to the N th section
L_{rem}	remaining driving distance
L_{max}	maximum AER
SOC_{rem}	variation range of the remaining capacity
SOC_{all}	total variation range
SOC_{max}	upper limit of the SOC
SOC_{min}	lower limit of the SOC
TSR	ratio between the engine output torque and required torque of power source
V_{mean}	average speed
r_{drive}	cruise time ratio

I. INTRODUCTION

Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle (PHEVs) not only inherit all advantages of conventional Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs), but also can be charged from the power grid, thus supplying a certain All-Electric Range (AER). It is equally and even more pivotal to design effective Energy Management Strategies (EMSs) for PHEVs, compared to that of conventional HEVs, thereby achieving proper energy allocation between different energy sources (e.g. Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) and battery). EMSs are of great importance for improving fuel economy, reducing emission and extending the battery lifespan, and therefore are widely researched by academia and industry [1].

EMSs of PHEVs can be mainly divided into two categories, i.e., the Charge Depletion-Charge Sustaining (CD-CS) scheme and blended strategies [2]. A demonstration in terms of the variation trajectory of battery State of Charge (SOC) based on two categories is shown in Fig. 1 [3]. Obviously, the CD-CS scheme is direct and easy to implement. In the CD mode, the vehicle is driven mainly by the motor and the engine is only started when the required driving power exceeds peak output of the motor. After entering the CS mode, the vehicle, similar to conventional HEVs, is driven together by the engine and motor with the target of optimizing operating efficiency of the engine and meanwhile regulating the battery SOC near the setting low threshold. The CD-CS scheme is independent of driving conditions and optimal controlling algorithms; and in other words, it acts blindly. If the preplanned driving range is less than the current AER, certainly, the energy only released by the battery can satisfy the driving demand. However, if the scheduled driving range is more than current AER, the

vehicle will switch to the CS mode after the SOC drops to the setting threshold. Given this, it is difficult, and even impossible, to achieve the optimal control due to the simple energy allocation framework [4].

Fig. 1. The SOC curve of different control strategies.

To overcome limitations of the CD-CS scheme, blended EMSs are put forward, which distribute electrical energy evenly throughout the whole driving process and try to discharge the battery gradually until its SOC drops to the low threshold in the end of trip. Blended strategies can potentially attain significant fuel economy improvement by globally optimizing the energy management and yet remain challenging to implement in real application. A common knowledge is that blended EMSs rely on detailed or rough trip information, such as driving condition and/ or overall trip distance/ duration, to achieve the global energy allocation of PHEVs. Currently, blended EMSs are mainly divided into two categories, i.e., optimization based algorithms and intelligent algorithms. Given the detailed trip information, energy management of PHEVs turns out to be a nonlinear optimal sequential decision problem. As such, typical optimal theories, such as Dynamic Programming (DP) [5], Pontryagin's Minimum Principle (PMP) [6], Quadratic Programming (QP) [7] and convex optimization [8], have been widely employed [9]. Additionally, instantaneous optimization algorithms, such as Equivalent Consumption Minimization Strategy (ECMS), are also widely researched due to their capability of immediate optimization of energy allocation. The ECMS can convert electric energy into fuel consumption with a predetermined coefficient, referred to as the equivalent factor, which is strongly coupled with the trip information [10]. Moreover, intelligent algorithms are also popular and recognized as possible solutions to EMSs. Typical manners include Neural Networks (NNs) [11], Fuzzy Logic (FL) algorithms [12], Genetic Algorithm (GA) [13], Simulated Annealing (SA) algorithm [14], and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [15]. They have been applied individually or jointly to find the suboptimal, or even optimal, solutions to energy allocation of PHEVs by referring to trip information [16]. To sum up, for blended EMSs, an indispensable task is to obtain the global trip information with the format of detailed traffic information or rough knowledge such as the total driving duration and distance.

In this context, trip information and driving condition identification are progressively introduced with the help of modern transportation systems and positioning system [17], such as the Global Positioning System (GPS), Intelligent Transportation System (ITS), and Geographical Information System (GIS). Previous discussions reveal that the trip information needs to be critically referred for optimizing the vehicle power allocation [18]. Additionally, prediction algorithms also attract wide attention thanks to the ability of forecasting a short-term velocity according to historical driving information and drivers' preferences. In [19], the fuzzy recognition is performed to classify driving cycles into three types, and DP is introduced to optimize the fuel consumption with these three types of cycles. According to the optimization results, real-time control rules are extracted, and the corresponding control strategies are constructed with respect to different road types to attain fast implementation. In [20], a Markov model is built to predict the future traffic state of the vehicle, and GA is harnessed to optimize the parameters of fuzzy model under different traffic conditions. In [21], the ITS and NN is incorporated to predict future driving conditions, and the Model Prediction Control (MPC) algorithm is applied to improve fuel economy of PHEVs and strengthen control adaptability. However, precise prediction based on MPC leads to considerable calculation intensity, thus possibly hindering online implementation potential. Alternatively, related researches employ fusion algorithms to overcome shortcomings of the single method and further improve the prediction performance [22]. Moreover, typical statistical and intelligent methods, such as Markov chain [23] and Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithms [24], may provide preferable real-time prediction; however, most of the time they only consider influence of driving conditions [25]. To summarize, the global long-term driving planning is vital to achieve the overall optimization of vehicle operation, and likewise the immediate driving condition identification is also imperative to ensure instantaneous optimality of EMSs. The best choice is to incorporate both the trip information and driving condition identification into the energy management of PHEVs. Additionally, the EMS should feature strong adaption to different driving conditions with the capability of real-time implementation.

Motivated by this, this study proposes a blended strategy that can overcome poor adaptability and unsatisfactory real-time performance of typical EMSs of PHEVs. Moreover, the proposed strategy can achieve online control of the target PHEV with near-optimal fuel economy considering different driving conditions and trip distances. To this end, DP is firstly leveraged to conduct offline global optimization of energy management of PHEVs. Then, the K-means clustering method is applied to identify the driving condition online by cooperation of GPS and GIS, and the influence to optimal energy management of PHEVs incurred by different

driving patterns and driving distance is investigated. On this basis, a blended EMS is designed to attain the real-time energy allocation of powertrain with incorporation of the identified driving conditions and extracted rules including the engine on/ off rule, shifting strategy and torque distribution scheme. Simulation results reveal that the built strategy features approximate fuel economy under different driving conditions, compared with the offline optimal solution searched by DP, and fast calculation speed, which is quite close to that of the CD-CS scheme. The main contributions of this paper are attributed to the following three aspects: 1) The driving cycle type and equivalent driving distance coefficient are selected as the feature parameters to characterize the driving cycle, and their influence on the optimal control is addressed. 2) The blended EMS considering the driving conditions and extracted rules is formulated including the engine on/ off rules, shifting strategies of transmission and torque distribution schemes. 3) The proposed strategy can attain preferable fuel economy with real-time application potential.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II models the vehicle powertrain and its main components, and details the calculation process of DP. Section III explains the built strategy incorporating the driving condition, and moreover extracts the optimal rules. Section IV discusses influences of driving cycles and driving distance, application of the control strategy and simulation validation. Section V draws the main conclusion of this study.

II. GLOBAL OPTIMAL ENERGY MANAGEMENT STRATEGY FOR PHEV

This section presents the powertrain configuration and constructs a global offline optimal EMS for the PHEV based on DP. To attain it, the vehicle and main powertrain components are modeled in detail.

A. Powertrain System of the PHEV

The PHEV studied in this paper is equipped with a parallel configured powertrain, as shown in Fig. 2. The engine and Integrated Starter Generator (ISG) are coaxially connected to drive a Dual-Clutch Transmission (DCT), which includes six speed ratios. Furthermore, a two-speed final drive is imbedded to modulate the speed and torque. Direct analysis indicates that in the studied PHEV, five working modes exist including the charging mode, engine driving mode, electric driving mode, hybrid driving mode, and regenerative braking mode. Table I specifies the basic parameters of the PHEV, which stem from on a product PHEV developed by Chongqing Changan Automobile Ltd [26].

Fig. 2. The powertrain configuration of the PHEV.

Table I Basic parameters of the PHEV

Item	Parameter	Value
Vehicle	Vehicle quality (no load) (kg)	1325
	Vehicle quality (full load) (kg)	1700
	Frontal area (m ²)	2.275
	Drag coefficient	0.3146
	Tire rolling radius (m)	0.308
	Rolling resistance coefficient	0.00995
ISG	Peak power (kW)	33
	Maximum torque (N·m)	140
Engine	Maximum power (kW)	80
	Maximum torque (N·m)	140
Lithium-ion battery	Capacity (Ah)	38.5
	Rated voltage (V)	288
DCT	speed ratio i1/i2/i3/i4/i5/i6	3.917/2.429/1.436/1.021/0.848/0.667
	final drive speed ratio a1/a2	3.762/4.158

1) Engine Model

In this study, an interpolation model is built to describe the relationship among the fuel rate of engine, torque and speed. The engine fuel rate data under different torque and speed are acquired through the calibration experiment conducted in Chongqing Changan Automobile Ltd, as shown in Fig. 3. By applying the linear interpolation, the engine fuel consumption can be determined [27].

Fig. 3. Engine fuel consumption map.

2) Motor Model

Similarly, according to the experiment data acquired in the test-bed [28], the spline interpolation method

is leveraged to describe the relationship among the efficiency, torque and speed of the motor, as shown in Fig.

4. We can find that the maximum efficiency of motor is more than 90%, and most of the time the efficiency is greater than 80%.

Fig. 4. ISG motor efficiency map.

3) Battery Model

In this paper, an internal resistance model is considered to characterize the electric performance of the battery. The model mainly consists of an Open Circuit Voltage (OCV) source and a resistance connected in series topology [29]. Note that all the data are acquired by our calibration experiment. The relationship of the electromotive force of battery and the charge and discharge internal resistance with respect to the SOC is shown in Fig. 5. The OCV increases from 291 V to 346 V when the SOC varies from 0 to 1. The internal resistance variation appears like a convex quadratic equation and shows the minimum value when the SOC equals around 0.5.

Fig. 5. Characteristic curves of power battery.

4) Vehicle Model

The required power of vehicle can be expressed as:

$$P_v = \frac{1}{3600\eta_t} (Mgf \cos(\alpha) + \frac{C_D A u^2}{21.15} + Mg \sin(\alpha) + \delta M \frac{du}{dt}) u \quad (1)$$

where M is the vehicle mass, f means the rolling resistance coefficient, α expresses the road grade, C_D denotes the air drag coefficient, A indicates the frontal area of the vehicle, u is the vehicle speed, δ is the correction coefficient of rotating mass, and η_t is the transmission system efficiency.

B. Global Optimization Based on DP

To solve energy management of the PHEV, first, it is imperative to determine the state variables, controlling inputs and discretization interval. According to the powertrain structure of studied PHEV, the fuel consumption cost is considered as the optimal target, and the frequent shifting of transmission is added as a penalty function. After setting the cost function, constraints and controlling variables, the global optimal solution can be searched based on inverse solution and forward optimization of DP.

1) Parameter Settings of DP

To guarantee optimization of the DP, the engine torque T_e and transmission ratio i_{DCT} are considered as the control variables. T_e can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} T_{req} = T_v / i_{DCT} \\ T_m = T_{req} - T_e \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where T_v is the vehicle demand torque and T_{req} is the demand torque of the energy source. All the parameters and discrete precision are shown in Table II, in which T_{all} denotes the duration of the driving cycle. It is necessary to note that the lower limit of SOC is set to 0.3, and in other words, the maximum Depth of Discharge (DOD) is 0.7.

Table II Parameter setting and discretization of PHEV for application of DP

Parameter	Variable	Discrete precision
Stage	Time (t)	[0:1: T_{all}]
Status	SOC	[0.3:0.005:0.9]
Control variable	Engine torque (T_e)	[0:2:140]
	Speed ratio of DCT (i)	[14.7358 10.0998 5.4022 4.2453 3.1902 2.7734]

2) Optimization of the Objective Function

According to Bellman's optimization theory, the objective function can be formulated as:

$$J = \sum_{k=1}^N L(x_k, u_k) \quad (3)$$

where J denotes the total cost for optimization; L indicates the instantaneous cost at each step; N is the total steps; x_k and u_k express the system state and controlling policies, respectively. The target in this study is to improve the fuel economy and meanwhile avoid the DCT from frequent shifting actions. Hence, L is composed of two items, i.e., the fuel consumption and the penalty of shifting restriction, as:

$$\begin{cases} L(x_k, u_k) = L_c(x_k, u_k) + L_g(x_k, u_k) \\ L_c(k) = P_f \cdot Q_{fuel}(k) + P_e \cdot Q_{ele}(k) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$L_g(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & |i_{k+1} - i_k| = 0 \\ \gamma & |i_{k+1} - i_k| = 1 \\ \inf & |i_{k+1} - i_k| > 1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where L_c is the instantaneous operating cost, L_g is the instantaneous cost for gear shifting, and P_f expresses the price of gasoline per liter, and equals CNY 7.8 in this study. $Q_{fuel}(k)$ denotes the instantaneous fuel consumption, and P_e represents the price of electricity per kwh. $Q_{ele}(k)$ is the instantaneous electricity consumption, and γ means the penalty factor for frequent gear shifting. To apply the DP, the cost function J is formulated, as:

$$J = \sum_{k=1}^N L(x_k, u_k) \quad (6)$$

In addition, the following constraints are imposed, as:

$$\begin{cases} T_{e_min} \leq T_e \leq T_{e_max} \\ n_{e_min} \leq n_e \leq n_{e_max} \\ T_{m_min} \leq T_m \leq T_{m_max} \\ n_{m_min} \leq n_m \leq n_{m_max} \\ SOC_{min} \leq SOC \leq SOC_{max} \\ |P_{battery}| \leq P_{battery_max} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where the subscripts min and max denote the corresponding minimum value and maximum value of each variable.

3) Solution of the DP

To implement the DP, the whole space is divided into a number of segments, which can be optimized individually by adding the former optimal cost value. In particular, the optimization problem of the N -1th segment can be formulated as:

$$J_{N-1}^*(x_{N-1}) = \min[L(x_{N-1}, u_{N-1})] \quad (8)$$

where N denotes the total amount of segments. In the k th ($0 \leq k < N - 1$) section, the optimization problem turns into:

$$J_k^*(x_k) = \min[L(x_k, u_k) + J_{k+1}^*(x_{k+1})] \quad (9)$$

where $J_k^*(x_k)$ denotes the minimum operating cost when the system changes from the k th section to the N th section with the initial state x_k .

III. DYNAMIC PROGRAMMING BASED BLENDED ENERGY MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

It is well acknowledged that the driving condition and driving distance can affect the optimal energy management of PHEVs. By merging the driving condition identification algorithm and GPS, a real-time blended EMS incorporating influences of driving conditions is proposed to improve the fuel economy of target PHEV under different driving conditions. As depicted in Fig. 6, the whole framework of algorithm is comprised of four parts: 1) principle analysis of the driving conditions, 2) extraction and determination of the dynamic control algorithm, 3) acquisition of real driving conditions, and 4) regulation of real-time control policy.

Fig. 6. Schematic of blended real-time control strategy for PHEV.

As can be seen in Fig. 6, the DP is firstly employed to find the offline optimal solution according to the process detailed in Section II. Then, different characteristics of driving conditions as well as the driving distance are discussed, and the real-time control rules based on the driving condition are extracted according to the principle factors that may influence the energy management efficiency. Thereinto, the K-means clustering

algorithm is harnessed to acquire the driving information together with GPS. Finally, the control rules are regulated in terms of the real-time driving information, thereby achieving online energy management of the vehicle.

A. Driving Condition Analysis

As discussed before, driving conditions account for an important role in design of EMS. According to the clustering analysis of driving conditions, we finally divided them into four categories according to the average speed and congestion status, as shown in Fig. 7. As can be observed, the average velocity gradually increases, and inversely the congested conditions decreases.

Fig. 7. Typical driving conditions.

In addition, the driving distance also generates certain influence to the design of blended EMS. However, it is meaningless that only the driving distance is considered, and moreover, the initial SOC of battery is also critical to determine the AER. To investigate influences of different driving distances on the optimal EMS of PHEV, an equivalent distance factor L_{equ} , expressed in (10), is proposed by considering the SOC and applied to illustrate the current all-electric driving distance and assist in planning the SOC decline trajectory [30].

$$\begin{cases} L_{equ} = \frac{SOC_{rem} / SOC_{all}}{L_{rem} / L_{max}} \\ SOC_{rem} = SOC_t - SOC_{min} \\ SOC_{all} = SOC_{max} - SOC_{min} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where L_{rem} denotes the remaining driving distance; L_{max} represents the maximum AER; SOC_{rem} expresses the variation range of the remaining capacity; SOC_{all} denotes the total variation range; and SOC_{max} and SOC_{min} express the upper and lower limits of SOC, i.e., 0.9 and 0.3, respectively. During the actual driving process, the driver can obtain the mileage information such as L_{rem} and L_{max} through the GPS and GIS. Here, $L_{equ} = 1$ indicates that the SOC is large enough and the residual energy of the battery can sustain the remaining trip. In this circumstance, the engine does not engage in driving the vehicle. With the decrement of L_{equ} , the engine needs to start to supply the supplementary driving energy and meanwhile the battery SOC gradually declines to the low threshold.

B. Extraction of Optimal Energy Management Rules

In this study, we define the basic rules in terms of the start power of engine, gear shifting rules and torque distribution of the engine and motor. Based on the optimal results solved by DP, the optimal rules are extracted by fully taking account of different driving conditions.

1) Selection of Basic Control Rules

Proper engagement of the engine can facilitate motor to drive the vehicle with higher efficiency. Indeed, the engine start/stop scheme is one of the key control strategies of PHEVs [31]. The transmission gearshift ratio and engine torque distribution scheme can effectively adjust the operating state of PHEV's energy source, so as to improve the operating efficiency of the engine and motor simultaneously. Consequently, the engine starting power P_{on} , transmission ratio i_{DCT} , and engine torque distribution ratio TSR formulated in (11), are selected as basic control parameters. i_{DCT} indexes the shift schedule which is divided into electric driving mode and engine participation mode, and the latter includes hybrid driving mode, engine driving mode and the driving and charging mode.

$$TSR = \frac{T_e}{T_{req}} \quad (11)$$

where TSR denotes the ratio between the engine output torque and required torque of power source. $TSR > 1$ indicates that the engine output torque is greater than the demand torque, and the PHEV is under the driving and charging mode. $TSR = 1$ denotes that the engine output torque equals the demand torque, and the vehicle is under the engine driving mode; and $TSR < 1$ represents that the engine torque is less than the demanded torque, and the vehicle is in the hybrid driving mode.

2) Optimal Control Rules Based on DP

Four representative driving cycles, as shown in Fig. 7, are simulated and meanwhile DP is applied. In addition, the equivalent travel distance coefficient matrix is constructed by calculating L_{equ} in terms of different SOC. Taking the fourth typical driving cycle as an example, the equivalent driving distance coefficient matrix under the specific driving cycle is shown in Fig. 8. As before, $L_{equ} = 1$ indicates that the engine is off all the time; and $L_{equ} < 1$ implies that the engine needs to participate in driving the vehicle.

Fig. 8. Equivalent travel distance coefficient matrix for the fourth typical driving cycle.

Fig. 9 shows the optimal control decision matrix obtained by DP for the fourth driving cycle. By extracting the controlling commands according to the equivalent driving distance coefficient matrix, the influences of L_{equ} on optimal control is analyzed; and by applying the equivalent travel distance coefficient matrix and optimal controlling commands matrix depicted in Figs. 8 and 9, the optimal control with different coefficients for each stage can be investigated. In the k th stage, the extraction process is illustrated in Fig. 10. According to the engine torque and speed ratio of the optimal solution, the optimal control decision matrices with different L_{equ} can be calculated. Repeat the above steps until the extraction of the optimal control strategy in all stages is completed.

Fig. 9. The optimal control decision matrix solved for the fourth typical driving cycle.

Fig. 10. Optimal control extraction process for different equivalent driving distance coefficients.

C. Access to Real-Time Driving Condition

The blended strategy needs to obtain the driving information including the driving pattern and equivalent driving distance coefficient, of which the latter can be calculated based on (10). In this study, the identification of driving conditions is tackled by the K-means clustering algorithm. For the stochastic conditions, the characteristic parameters are extracted and applied. The Euclidean distance is calculated between each parameter and center of the corresponding driving condition. The basic data consisting of the real driving condition and standard driving cycle is divided into multi segments with each length of 150 s, and the average speed V_{mean} and cruise time ratio r_{drive} are extracted as characteristic parameters. The GA is employed to optimize the initial center of K-means clustering, and then the K-means clustering analysis is performed to obtain the final clustering center. Fig. 11 shows the sum of clustering samples and clustering results of the driving cycles. The basic driving cycle data is divided into four clusters, as distinguished by different colors. Furthermore, the cluster centers of these four types are calculated, and their coordinates are (3.672, 34.451), (11.681, 70.835), (18.317, 96.852) and (50.965, 99.124), respectively.

Fig. 11. Clustering samples and results of driving cycles.

The application process of the driving condition recognition is shown in Fig. 12. First, $V_{mean}(t)$ and $r_{drive}(t)$ in $(t-150, t)$ as well as the distance to each cluster center are calculated. Then, d_1, d_2, d_3 and d_4 are respectively calculated according to $V_{mean}(t), r_{drive}(t)$ and four center coordinates. By this manner, the driving condition is determined based on the minimum distance away from the centers. Next step, the simulation is conducted to validate the feasibility of proposed algorithm.

Fig. 12. Flow chart of driving cycle identification

IV. APPLICATION AND SIMULATION VALIDATION

To verify the effectiveness of built strategy, the influence of different driving conditions is firstly investigated in terms of the optimal energy management. On this basis, the proposed real-time EMS is applied according to the varying driving conditions, and as such, the sub-optimal energy management of PHEV is attained. In the study, to evaluate the performance of proposed strategy, we selected the DP to obtain the offline optimal solution and the traditional CD-CS strategy to find the most direct online management result.

A. Influences Analysis of Driving Conditions

To optimize the energy management of target PHEV with the consideration of different driving conditions and driving distances, four typical equivalent travel distance coefficients, i.e., 0.05, 0.35, 0.65, and 0.95, are extracted and compared. The main purpose of choosing these four values is to compare the optimal controlling parameters induced by the equivalent factor. These four coefficients are able to cover different equivalent driving coefficient ranges, and can fully evaluate the differences among the optimal control parameters within the equivalent driving coefficient interval of 0 to 1.

1) The Influences of Driving Conditions on the Engine Starting Power

Fig. 13 shows the engine operating states for the fourth type of driving condition with different equivalent driving distance coefficients. The vehicle power demand can be referred as the control decision for starting/stopping the engine. As can be seen, the starting power of the engine gradually decreases with L_{equ} . Therefore, the optimal starting decision of engine can be determined.

Fig. 13. Engine operating state with different equivalent driving distances under the fourth driving cycle.

The engine starting power of these four types of driving cycles under different equivalent driving distance coefficients are listed in Table III. We can find that the engine starting power of the first type of driving cycle is lowest, and that of the fourth type is highest due to the largest average required power.

Table III Engine starting power under different coefficients for four types of driving cycles

L_{equ}	Type 1 (kw)	Type 2 (kw)	Type 3 (kw)	Type 4 (kw)
0.95	8	15	15	32
0.65	7	9	8	23
0.35	5	6	5	16
0.05	3	3	2.5	8

2) The Influence of Driving Conditions on Shifting Schedule

In the electric driving mode, the shift schedules of four types of driving cycles are extracted according to the optimization results. Due to wide regulation range of the motor speed, the shifting schedules of four types

remain the same, and the driving conditions do not play any effect in shifting schedule. The speed ratio distribution in the electric driving mode during the fourth type condition is shown in Fig. 14, and the shift schedule is actually the upshift curve extracted according to the optimized speed ratio when L_{equ} is 0.95. It can be concluded that the shifting schedules under the different equivalent driving distance coefficients are almost the same, and only the operating points of motor will differ from each other.

Fig. 14. Speed ratio distribution of electric driving mode in the fourth type of driving cycle.

In the engine-starting mode, the shift schedules of the first three types are the same, whereas the fourth type is different thanks to the higher speed. As a result, we can summarize that the driving condition type will affect the shifting schedule in the engine-starting mode. The speed ratio distribution of engine-starting mode in the fourth type of driving cycle is shown in Fig. 15, and the upshift curve is extracted according to the engine speed ratio distribution when L_{equ} is 0.05. It can be seen that with the increment of L_{equ} , the shifting schedule extracted when L_{equ} equals 0.05 does not match the distribution of speed ratio. That said, the shifting schedule in the engine-starting mode is affected not only by the type of driving conditions, but also by the equivalent driving distance coefficient.

Fig. 15. Speed ratio distribution of engine starting mode in the fourth type of driving cycles.

3) The Influence of Driving Conditions on Torque Distribution Ratios

Fig. 16 shows the fitting results of the optimal torque distribution ratios of engine for four types of driving conditions under different equivalent driving distance coefficients. As can be observed, the optimal torque distribution ratios of engine locate in the vicinity of the same fitting curve and do not change obviously with L_{equ} . Therefore, the optimal engine torque distribution ratios are not affected by L_{equ} , and the engine torque distribution strategy can be implemented based on the fitted *TSR* curve. Fig. 17 plots the fitting results of optimal torque distribution ratios with different types of driving conditions. It can be found that there exists a large gap in the curve under different types of driving conditions. To conclude, the driving condition type can certainly the optimal engine torque distribution ratio, and Table IV lists the influence of different driving cycle types and different driving distance coefficients on the optimal control of the PHEV.

Fig. 16. *TSR* curve fitting results of different equivalent driving distance coefficients.

Fig. 17. Optimal *TSR* fitting curve under four types of driving cycles.

Table IV Influence on the optimal control of the PHEV

Driving cycle characteristics	Engine starting power	Shift schedule		Torque distribution ratio of the engine
		Electric driving mode	Engine starting mode	
Driving cycle type	1	0	1	1
Driving distance coefficient	1	0	1	0

Note: 1: showing influence; 0: no influence

B. Application of the Proposed Blended Strategy

According to the results discussed above, the influence of driving cycle type and driving distance on the optimal control can be quantified. On this basis, a real-time control strategy is applied by incorporating the engine starting decision, transmission ratio, and engine torque ratio based on identification of driving conditions,

respectively.

1) Engine On/Off Decision

Under each typical driving cycle shown in Fig. 7, ten discrete points are extracted from the equivalent driving distance coefficient between 0.05 and 0.95, and the engine starting-power fitted by the cubic interpolation under different coefficients can be formulated in (12) and plotted in Fig. 18.

$$P_{\text{on}} = p_1 \cdot L_{\text{equ}}^3 + p_2 \cdot L_{\text{equ}}^2 + p_3 \cdot L_{\text{equ}} + p_4 \quad (12)$$

where p_1 , p_2 , p_3 and p_4 denote the fitting coefficients.

Fig. 18. Engine starting power curve obtained by cubic interpolation fitting.

Here, the GA is introduced to optimize the four coefficients of engine-on power under four typical driving cycles. The maximum generation, population size, elite number and cross generation ratio of GA are set to 80, 100, 10, and 0.4, respectively. The optimization result of the driving cycle type 4 is shown in Fig. 19. As can be found, when the generation increases, the optimal fitness value decreases continuously and finally converges to the optimal value. The optimization results for these four driving cycles are listed in Table V.

Fig. 19. Optimization engine starting power curve under the fourth type of driving cycle.

Table V Optimization results of four coefficients

Driving cycle type	P_1	P_2	P_3	P_4
1	-8.1089	9.7210	3.3845	2.8904
2	-0.8418	4.1667	9.1940	2.5047
3	4.4678	7.6923	2.6054	2.3283
4	35.0136	-45.2567	43.9033	5.9759

The engine-starting power curve obtained after optimization is shown in Fig. 20. According to the identified driving condition and driving distance, the corresponding engine starting power curve is selected, and simultaneously the optimal starting power value of engine is determined.

Fig. 20. Engine starting power curve optimized by GA.

2) Design of the Shifting Schedule

Reasonable shift schedule can enable the engine to work in the high efficiency range. According to the previous analysis, the driving cycle type and driving distance do not influence the shifting schedule under the electric driving mode but will take effect in the engine starting mode. Therefore, according to the optimization result of DP, two types of shifting schedules are extracted in different driving cycle types, and the corresponding type of shifting schedule is selected according to the recognition result of driving conditions. For each type of shifting schedule, ten sub-shift schedules are extracted with equal intervals between the equivalent driving distance coefficient of 0.05 to 0.95.

3) Engine Torque Distribution Ratio

According to the research results, only the type of driving cycles will affect the optimal *TSR*. Its curve obtained by fitting interpolation and plotted in Fig. 17 can be referred for real-time control of the PHEV in terms of recognition result of the driving condition. Finally, according to the established real-time control rules, a blended real-time energy management strategy of PHEV is applied by fully considering the influence of driving

conditions and driving distance. Based on the current SOC value and power demand of the vehicle, an optimal engine operating state and torque distribution scheme between the engine and electric machine can be finally determined by applying the established sub-policy for the engine on/ off control, transmission shifting schedule, and engine torque distribution ratio. Thereinto, the engine working status can be controlled by the engine start/stop scheme; and the gear position of transmission can be regulated by the shifting strategy. Finally, the output torque of engine is determined according to the distribution scheme.

C. Performance Validation Based on Different Strategies

To validate the feasibility of built strategy, a comprehensive driving cycle is constructed with combination of the measured driving data and standard driving cycles. The built driving cycle and corresponding recognition results based on the K-means clustering algorithm are shown in Fig. 21. As can be observed, the cycle contains four different types, thereby effectively verifying adaptability of the proposed identification strategy.

Fig. 21. Comprehensive driving cycle and the identification results.

To further conduct performance analysis of the proposed algorithm, different initial SOC values are taken into account. The corresponding simulation results are listed in Table VI. It can be found that when the initial SOC ranges from 0.8 to 0.4, the DP and proposed algorithm can respectively improve the fuel economy by 14.3% to 18% and by 11.37% to 14.8%, compared to the CD-CS scheme, thus significantly improving the fuel economy of vehicle. To conclude, the simulation results manifest that the proposed strategy can realize the preferable performance, compared with the DP.

Table VI Simulation results of energy consumption cost

Initial SOC	DP		The proposed algorithm		CD-CS scheme
	Energy consumption cost (CNY)	Improvement (%)	Energy consumption cost (CNY)	Improvement (%)	Energy consumption cost (CNY)
0.8	4.69	15.34	4.74	14.44	5.54
0.7	6.71	14.3	6.94	11.37	7.83
0.6	8.9	17.21	9.21	14.33	10.75
0.5	11.25	18	11.69	14.8	13.72
0.4	13.77	16.65	14.4	12.83	16.52-

Taking the case of the initial SOC of 0.6 as an example, the calculation intensity and energy consumption based on the three algorithms are compared in Table VII. All the three strategies are programmed on a laptop equipped with an i5 processor. The calculation time of the CD-CS strategy, proposed algorithm and DP is 2.39 s, 3.55 s, and 493.27 s, respectively. The proposed algorithm achieves a preferable energy consumption cost, compared with DP, but with much faster calculation speed. In comparison with the CD-CS scheme, the energy consumption cost can be reduced dramatically; and yet the difference of computation duration is only 1.18 s. Fig. 22 compares the SOC trajectories based on the three strategies. The proposed strategy can deplete the electric energy in a blended manner according to the driving distance and discharges the battery gradually to the lower limit of the SOC when the trip ends. As can be seen, it drops faster in the marked ellipse; however, to avoid falling into the CD mode, the algorithm enables the SOC to drop slower afterwards. The remaining SOC variation profile looks similar to that of DP. As a result, the proposed strategy can plan decline of the SOC globally in a proper manner.

Table VII Comparison of the calculation time and energy consumption cost when the initial SOC is 0.6

Strategies	Calculation time (s)	Energy consumption cost (CNY)	Improvement (%)
DP	493.27	8.9	17.21
The proposed algorithm	3.55	9.21	14.33
CD-CS scheme	2.39	10.75	—

Fig. 22. The simulation results of the SOC under three control strategies.

Fig. 23 compared the engine torque based on the three control strategies. As can be seen, the engine participates in driving the vehicle through the whole driving process. The proposed strategy leads to similar operating time and torque output of the engine, compared with those of DP, indicating the engine starting power can be well adjusted according to the varying driving condition and driving distance. On the contrary, the CD-CS scheme cannot dynamically control the engine power according to the driving distance, and only blindly starts the engine to participate in vehicle drive after entering the CS mode.

Fig. 23. Engine torque simulation results for three control strategies.

Fig. 24 shows simulation results for the engine operating points based on the blended real-time control strategy and CD-CS control strategy. It can be clearly observed that the engine operating point of the blended real-time control strategy can be well distributed in the vicinity of high efficiency region, whereas most of operating points based on the CD-CS control strategy is stochastically distributed in the inefficient area. The operating efficiency map indicates that the regulated engine torque distribution ratio curve and shifting schedule can reasonably control the engine torque and speed under different driving conditions, proving effectiveness of the built algorithm. To sum up, the proposed blended strategy can regulate the battery SOC effectively and control the engine operating efficiently in real time with fast calculation, thereby leading to superior fuel economy and adaption to different driving conditions.

Fig. 24. Simulation results for engine operating points.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigates a blended real-time energy management strategy for the PHEV considering the influence of driving condition. First, DP is applied to optimize the energy management strategy for four typical driving cycles, and the global optimal control solution is achieved. Second, the driving cycle type and equivalent driving distance coefficient are selected as the characteristics of the driving condition, and the optimal control strategy is extracted and analyzed according to the global optimization result. Then, the K-means clustering algorithm is leveraged to identify the driving condition and a blended real-time control strategy is established based on the driving condition and driving distance. The real-time equivalent travel distance coefficient is calculated by the mileage information, and the control strategy is dynamically regulated in real time according to the driving conditions and driving distance. Simulation results show that the fuel economy of proposed strategy can be improved by 11.37% to 14.8%, compared with that of the CD-CS strategy, and is close to the global optimal fuel economy solved by DP. Moreover, the calculation time of the proposed strategy is only slightly longer than that of the CD-CS strategy, manifesting the feasibility of real-time control. In conclusion, the proposed strategy attains superior fuel economy, real-time implementation, and driving condition adaptability for energy management of PHEVs.

Next step work will focus on validation in the hardware-in-the-loop platform and the real vehicle test to further optimize the real-time performance of proposed algorithm. In addition, more research will be conducted to further improve the controlling performance of proposed algorithm by incorporating advantages of other intelligent methods.

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